

Working Women in Contemporary Society: Challenges

Dr. V.C. Priyadharshini

Assistant Professor

SFR College for Women, Sivakasi

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We may encounter many defeats
but we must not be defeated

- Maya Angelou.

Abstract

Today many people claim that the need to talk about empowerment or equal status for women in the society is outdated because; they feel that women have already been liberated enough. This is a highly absurd statement because even though some women today have reached a considerable place in the society through education, the struggle still continues only in a different form. One cannot deny the traditional form of subjugation that persists in our modern world despite the positive changes. Different kinds of challenges keep coming in the life of women especially in the case of working women. They are exposed to lots of new physiological, social and psychological challenges at the work place. This significantly impacts her life at home. This paper attempts to study the challenges faced by the working women of the contemporary society.

Keywords: Challenges, physiology, social, psychological.

Virginia Woolf a British writer in her book *The Room of One's own* writes about the importance of women having a room for herself at her home. This room can be used by her for understanding herself and to express her creative talents. Virginia Woolf throughout the book writes about the discrimination that women faced as a writer. She also discusses about a woman's relationship with a man, she writes, “Women have served all these centuries as looking glasses possessing the magic and delicious power of reflecting the figure of man at twice its natural size.” (p. 3) This book was written in the year 1929 and it's been almost a century and till now women at many home only 'reflect the figure of man at twice it's natural size.'

Women who try to liberate themselves from such a bond through a job, focus more on their individual talents and ideas are always looked down by the society unless and until she has a very strong support from her partner. Contrastingly when a working women who is either a divorcee or a widow or a single woman who has crossed her thirty tries to exhibit her talents in a potential way she is subjected to severe criticism. The stigma around this group of working women undoubtedly exists in today's society. Empowering such women and showing them the ways to stay strong is a new type of challenge that the people who fight for women's rights have to face today. Gone

are the days where the struggles faced by women were discussed under one category. There is an urgent need to awake ourselves and to analyze the different problems faced by the different groups of women in the contemporary society.

The problems that all these women commonly face at workplace cannot be ignored too. She has to balance her life inside and outside her workplace. The stress that she faces in her workplace can never be brought to her home because that will ruin her relationship with the different people at home. In some cases she cannot even go out even with her female colleagues without getting prior permission from everyone at home. This cannot be ignored as a simple issue. She is equally educated and sometimes even better but still she needs to maintain an emotional balance and hide her wishes. When she fails to compromise the consequence is very severe. Surprisingly even today we have families who do not like to send women for work. In cases like this it's double the fight. If she fails to be the 'balancing goddess' of the home in most cases it leads to divorce. Many women even resign from their favorite job only to take care of the family.

People might defend against the above said statements claiming, isn't that necessary for a balanced society? Sadly they fail to realize that women are also a part of this society and her will and wishes also matters. In fact she is the heart of the society and a healthy and a happy heart is necessary for healthy living. Another important challenge that women face at workplace is that she has to compete with her male colleagues when it comes to her career growth. Some people even assert, 'why not talk about equality here?' They fail to understand the different circumstances from which a woman comes for work. She goes through lots of physiological changes earlier than men. Her social responsibilities are higher when compared to a man. In a country like India where festivals and celebrations are part of life, a woman has to be socially active during these festivals maintaining her relationships with her kith and kin.

She also goes through lots of psychological difficulties. Some women have the natural ability to balance both family and workplaces but, in many cases women lose that balance thereby leading to poor psychological health. Many organizations in our country ignore this and do not even have a counseling centre for working women in their institutions. Organizations should consider establishing such centers inside the campus itself or at least organize programs related to the importance of mental health, so that their women employees might get professional help. Dr. Lynda Shaw, a Business Neuroscientist in her article, 'The Psychology of the Female Worker' comes up with another problem related to the psychology of men and women,

There are minute physical differences between the brains of the genders. For instance, women are more likely to have greater emotional intelligence and empathy because of having a larger limbic system. Both men and women are bullied in the workplace but women are more likely to take it personally and for it have a semi or permanent effect on their confidence because their larger limbic system means they are more likely to be in touch with emotions and are more vulnerable. (n.p).

She further adds even though this does not affect the competition much, the only thing that bothers is the treatment that women get in a workplace compared to her men counterpart, "Today the world economy would collapse without women working. Yet in 2010 International Labor Organization found that in 83 countries, women earn 10-30% less than men and it would take another 75 years for women to get paid equally around the globe." (n.p).

With all these physiological, social and psychological challenges surrounding her, a woman continues to stay strong as much as possible. Unfortunately harassment at workplace has also found its way and working women suffer a lot because of it. The 'me too' movement came as a shock and alarm to everyone in our country. Many men were even found guilty and this shook and questioned the security of women at workplace. Awareness regarding problems faced by women at

workplace should be seriously addressed and solved because if the society starts to feel that women are not safe outside then it will decide to keep them inside.

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